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**A multiplicative model for assessing the effectiveness of the anti-corruption
mechanism under wartime conditions**

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Abstract: The purpose of the article is to formalize the anti-corruption mechanism as a sequential institutional system and to develop a model for assessing its integral effectiveness under wartime conditions, taking into account the impact of wartime risk. The study also substantiates directions for strengthening the institutional role of financial intelligence in ensuring the economic security of the state.

The research is based on a systems approach, functional modeling, elements of reliability and risk theory, structural-logical analysis, and the comparative legal method to assess institutional interaction within the anti-corruption mechanism. The formalization is implemented through the construction of a multiplicative model of integral effectiveness incorporating a wartime risk coefficient and an institutional sensitivity parameter.

The anti-corruption mechanism is interpreted as a system of sequential transformations in which financial intelligence performs the function of an analytical core, reducing uncertainty and forming the basis for subsequent procedural decisions. The expediency of multiplicative aggregation of institutional effectiveness is substantiated, and a wartime risk coefficient with an institutional sensitivity parameter is introduced. Directions for institutional and regulatory improvement of financial intelligence are systematized with the aim of enhancing coherence within the anti-corruption chain and reducing its vulnerability under wartime pressure.

The proposed formalized approach enables quantitative assessment of anti-corruption effectiveness and identification of critical points for institutional strengthening. Under wartime conditions, financial intelligence acquires an expanded functional role, transforming from a financial monitoring instrument into a structural component of the state's economic security system.

Keywords: anti-corruption mechanism; financial intelligence; wartime risk; institutional resilience; economic security; multiplicative model; public finance governance; institutional effectiveness.

**Мультиплікативна модель оцінювання ефективності антикорупційного
механізму в умовах війни**

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Abstract: Метою статті є удосконалення антикорупційного механізму як послідовної та взаємопов'язаної інституційної системи та розроблення мультиплікативної моделі оцінювання його інтегральної ефективності в умовах війни, з урахуванням впливу воєнного ризику та інституційної чутливості. Окрему увагу приділено обґрунтуванню напрямів інституційного посилення ролі фінансової розвідки в системі забезпечення економічної безпеки держави.

Методологічною основою дослідження є системний підхід, функціональне моделювання, елементи теорії ризику, структурно-логічний аналіз і порівняльно-правовий метод для оцінювання інституційної взаємодії складових антикорупційного механізму. Формалізація здійснена шляхом побудови мультиплікативної моделі інтегральної ефективності, що враховує коефіцієнт воєнного ризику та параметр інституційної чутливості, а також передбачає можливість диференційованого впливу ризику на окремі етапи антикорупційного ланцюга.

Антикорупційний механізм інтерпретовано як систему послідовних функціонально взаємопов'язаних перетворень, у якій фінансова розвідка виконує роль аналітичного ядра, забезпечуючи редукцію невизначеності та формування доказової бази для подальших процесуальних рішень. Обґрунтовано доцільність мультиплікативного агрегування ефективності інституційних блоків як відображення їх структурної незамінності та кумулятивного характеру втрат у разі зниження спроможності окремих ланок. Систематизовано напрями інституційно-правового вдосконалення діяльності фінансової розвідки, спрямовані на підвищення узгодженості антикорупційного механізму та зниження його вразливості в умовах воєнного навантаження.

Запропонований підхід дозволяє здійснювати кількісне оцінювання результативності антикорупційної системи, ідентифікувати критичні точки її посилення та обґрунтовувати заходи з підвищення інституційної стійкості. В умовах війни фінансова розвідка трансформується з інструмента фінансового моніторингу у структурний елемент системи економічної безпеки держави, що забезпечує збереження публічних ресурсів та фінансову стійкість у період воєнного і післявоєнного розвитку.

Keywords: антикорупційний механізм; фінансова розвідка; воєнний ризик; інституційна стійкість; економічна безпека; мультиплікативна модель; публічні фінанси; ефективність системи.

Problem statement. The functioning of the anti-corruption mechanism is traditionally examined through the prism of its institutional architecture and the distribution of competences among individual authorities. At the same time, insufficient attention is paid to the systemic interdependence of its components and to the impact of weaknesses in individual links on the overall effectiveness of anti-corruption efforts. The issue of quantitatively reflecting the interrelationship between financial-analytical detection, criminal-law qualification, judicial verification, and asset management as successive stages of a unified process remains unresolved.

This problem becomes particularly acute under martial law, when the concentration of public financial resources in the areas of defense and reconstruction increases, external risk pressure intensifies, and the detection of corrupt financial flows becomes more complex. The wartime context transforms the nature of threats, increases the latency of financial offenses, and simultaneously amplifies the consequences of institutional inconsistency. In the absence of a comprehensive systemic approach to evaluating the effectiveness of the anti-corruption mechanism, it is difficult to substantiate directions for its institutional strengthening and to identify critical points of vulnerability.

Thus, there arises a need to formalize the anti-corruption mechanism as a sequential institutional system and to develop an instruments for assessing its effectiveness, taking into account the impact of wartime risk. Addressing this task provides a foundation for the scientifically grounded specification of the role of financial intelligence in ensuring the systemic resilience of the state.

Recent research analysis. Research on anti-corruption issues encompasses a broad spectrum of theoretical and applied approaches. In particular, V. Franchuk, S. Melnyk, V. Hobela and others [1] substantiate the theoretical and methodological foundations for the formation of a security environment as a systemic category, emphasizing the necessity of integrated risk management in the financial and economic sphere. O. Bilotskyi, I. Pidberezskyi, and V. Darvai [2] examine the socio-

economic consequences of corruption for the development of Ukrainian society, highlighting its destructive impact on the institutional capacity of the state.

The issue of financial monitoring as an instrument for counteracting the legalization of criminal proceeds is explored by Kh. Vozniakovska [3], who defines its significance in detecting suspicious financial transactions within the AML framework. In the context of threats to economic security, V. Hobela and S. Melnyk [4] analyze offshoring as a factor contributing to capital outflows and weakening the state's financial resilience. The social and institutional aspects of corruption development within public policy are addressed in the works of O. Dyka and K. Naumchuk [5], who emphasize the importance of coherence among anti-corruption mechanisms.

The international experience in combating money laundering and terrorist financing is systematized by V. Kovalenko, S. Dmytrov, and A. Yezhov [6], who focus on FATF standards and the institutional specialization of financial intelligence units. N. Moskalenko [7] generalizes global models of AML/CFT systems, underscoring the importance of interagency coordination and the adaptation of national mechanisms to international requirements. Administrative and legal issues of anti-corruption policy in Ukraine are examined by V. Nastiuk, V. Bielievitseva, and O. Klok [8], who draw attention to regulatory fragmentation and the complexity of practical application of legal instruments.

Issues related to the formation and implementation of state anti-corruption policy are studied by K. Naumchuk [9], who identifies its strategic orientations and institutional mechanisms. D. Pavlov [10] substantiates the interconnection between anti-money laundering efforts and the safeguarding of economic security, considering financial monitoring as a component of security policy. The global experience of specialized anti-corruption institutions and the specific features of shaping a national anti-corruption model are summarized by O. Yarmysh [16].

An analysis of the regulatory framework in the fields of corruption prevention and financial monitoring [11–14] indicates that an institutional foundation of the anti-

corruption system has been established. At the same time, the legal domain still contains unresolved issues concerning the procedural status of analytical materials, the clarity of interagency interaction mechanisms, and the development of a formalized approach to assessing the effectiveness of the anti-corruption mechanism.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Despite the substantial body of scholarly contributions, most studies focus either on individual institutions or on specific legal aspects of combating corruption and money laundering. The issue of formalizing the anti-corruption mechanism as a system of interconnected transformations, with a quantitative representation of its integral effectiveness and due consideration of wartime risk, remains insufficiently developed.

The absence of such a model complicates the identification of critical bottlenecks within the system and limits the substantiation of directions for the institutional strengthening of financial intelligence.

Research Objectives and Tasks. The aim of the study is to formalize the anti-corruption mechanism as an institutional system and to develop a model for assessing its integral effectiveness, taking into account the impact of wartime risk, as well as to substantiate directions for improving the state's financial intelligence framework.

To achieve this aim, the following tasks are envisaged:

- to substantiate the expediency of interpreting the anti-corruption mechanism as a system of functionally interconnected transformations;
- to develop a formalized model of integral effectiveness that reflects the interdependence of institutional components;
- to determine the impact of the wartime environment on the performance of the anti-corruption chain and on its sensitivity parameters;
- to specify directions for institutional and legal improvement of financial intelligence activity from the perspective of systemic resilience.

Results. The systematization of directions for improving financial intelligence makes it possible to move from a descriptive analysis of its functions to a

formalization of its role within the integrated anti-corruption mechanism of the state. In this context, financial intelligence is viewed not as an auxiliary instrument of financial monitoring, but as the analytical core of the anti-corruption infrastructure, ensuring the transformation of large volumes of financial transactions into structured evidentiary information.

The anti-corruption process should be interpreted as a sequence of functionally interconnected transformations forming a continuous institutional chain: from the financial system, within which monetary flows are generated, to asset management and the achievement of a final economic outcome (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The chain of combating corruption and the role of financial intelligence in it

Source: developed by authors.

In functional terms, the anti-corruption chain may be represented as a composition of transformations:

$$R = f AM \circ f J \circ f LE \circ f FIU (S)$$

де S – the set of financial transactions in the national economy;

$f FIU$ – the function of analytical selection and structuring of risky transactions;

$f LE$ – criminal-law qualification;

$f J$ – judicial verification;

$f AM$ – asset management and recovery;

R – the integral result of anti-corruption impact.

The key element of this model is the financial intelligence function, which reduces uncertainty by isolating, from the entire set of transactions, a subset of potentially risky financial flows:

$$S \rightarrow S^*; S^* \subset S$$

The quality of this analytical reduction determines the effectiveness of subsequent stages of the anti-corruption process, since errors at the initial stage are cumulative and intensify at higher institutional levels.

The integral effectiveness of the anti-corruption chain depends on the performance of each of its blocks. If the effectiveness of financial intelligence, law enforcement, the judiciary, and asset management are denoted respectively as e_{FIU} , e_{LE} , e_J , e_{AM} then the overall system effectiveness may be expressed as:

$$E = (e_{FIU} * e_{LE} * e_J * e_{AM})$$

The choice of a multiplicative form of aggregation is grounded in the principles of the systems approach and risk theory. In the proposed interpretation, the anti-corruption mechanism functions as a sequential system of transformations in which each institutional block constitutes a necessary condition for achieving the final result. In reliability theory, such systems are classified as series systems, where the probability of successful functioning equals the product of the probabilities of operability of each element.

Transferring this logic to the anti-corruption model implies that the effectiveness of financial intelligence, law enforcement, judicial proceedings, and asset management represents interdependent events. Low effectiveness at any stage cannot be fully compensated by high effectiveness at others, since a disruption at one level leads to losses at subsequent stages.

An additive model would be methodologically incorrect in this context, as it would imply substitutability of institutional blocks, whereas in the real anti-

corruption process they are functionally sequential and structurally non-substitutable. From the standpoint of risk theory, the multiplicative form also reflects the cumulative nature of efficiency losses: each additional limiting factor proportionally reduces the integral outcome according to its own level of capacity.

Thus, the application of a multiplicative model adequately reflects the systemic nature of the anti-corruption mechanism, highlights its sensitivity to institutional bottlenecks, and ensures conceptual consistency with the subsequent introduction of a wartime risk coefficient. In this sense, the proposed formalization is not merely a mathematical abstraction but a logical continuation of the systemic interpretation of the anti-corruption chain as a sequential institutional construct.

The multiplicative form of this relationship underscores that even high performance of individual components cannot compensate for low effectiveness at any single stage. Therefore, the effectiveness of financial intelligence must be considered within the broader context of institutional coherence of the entire system.

Particular importance attaches to analyzing the functioning of this model under martial law. The wartime context generates additional external risk pressure on the anti-corruption mechanism due to the concentration of significant budgetary resources in the defense sector. These factors increase the probability of the emergence of corrupt financial flows while simultaneously complicating their detection.

To formalize this influence, it is appropriate to introduce a wartime risk coefficient $W \in [0,1]$, reflecting the intensity of the external risk environment. The integral effectiveness of the anti-corruption chain under martial law then takes the form:

$$E_w = (e_{FIU} * e_{LE} * e_J * e_{AM}) * (1 - w)$$

Thus, the wartime factor acts as a diminishing multiplier of systemic effectiveness. However, the impact of war is not identical across different state systems, which necessitates the introduction of an institutional sensitivity parameter: $\alpha > 0$. In this case, the generalized model becomes:

$$E_w = (e_{FIU} * e_{LE} * e_J * e_{AM}) * (1 - W)^\alpha$$

The parameter α reflects the level of institutional resilience: $\alpha > 1$, wartime risk causes a disproportionate decline in effectiveness, characteristic of fragmented systems with low coordination; conversely, when $0 < \alpha < 1$, the system demonstrates a relative capacity to absorb external shocks.

A more detailed modification of the model allows for a differentiated impact of wartime risk on each stage of the anti-corruption chain:

$$E_w = (e_{FIU}(1 - w_{FIU}) * e_{LE}(1 - w_{LE}) * e_J(1 - w_J) * e_{AM}(1 - w_{AM}))$$

де w_i – denotes the specific wartime risk affecting the respective institutional block.

Such an approach makes it possible to identify systemic bottlenecks and substantiate targeted directions for institutional strengthening.

In this context, financial intelligence performs not only an analytical but also a compensatory function. Accordingly, the modernization of financial intelligence under martial law extends beyond the traditional AML paradigm and acquires the features of an instrument for ensuring the state's economic and financial security.

The proposed formalized model enables the interpretation of the anti-corruption mechanism as an integrated functional system, provides a quantitative explanation of the influence of the wartime environment on its effectiveness, and substantiates the need for institutional integration of financial intelligence into the continuous anti-corruption chain—from financial-analytical detection to judicial decision-making and subsequent asset management.

The described model creates an analytical foundation for specifying directions of institutional improvement, as it allows for the identification of critical interaction points among its components and the assessment of their impact on the system's integral effectiveness. Taking into account identified functional gaps and risk zones, a set of measures is proposed to strengthen coordination, procedural coherence, and adaptability of the anti-corruption mechanism under wartime pressure (Table 1).

Table 1.

Directions of institutional and legal improvement of financial intelligence activities

Institutional level	Direction of improvement	Objectives in the model / KPIs	Expected effect
FIU of Ukraine – NABU / SAPO	<p>Standardization of analytical materials formats and joint determination of risk priorities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ normative definition of the status of analytical reference; ✓ fixing minimum requirements for its content; ✓ establishing the procedure for its use as evidence 	<p>Objective: $\uparrow eLEe$; $\uparrow eFIU$</p> <p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ share of analytical reports used for procedural actions; ✓ average time from transfer of material to procedural processing (days); ✓ share of materials recognized as unsuitable (%) 	Increasing the procedural suitability of analytical materials
FIU of Ukraine – HACC	<p>Adaptation of analytical products to the needs of the trial:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ register of high-risk financial profiles; ✓ coordination of annual sectoral priorities (defense, post-war reconstruction, public procurement); ✓ definition of indicators of interaction effectiveness 	<p>Objective: $\uparrow eJ$</p> <p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ proportion of cases – accepted as evidence (%); ✓ proportion of effective decisions in cases (%); ✓ cases of contradictory interpretation of evidence / frequency of returns for revision 	Increasing the share of effective court decisions
FIU of Ukraine – ARMA	<p>Early involvement of the Financial Institution in asset identification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ creation of an algorithm for early marking of risky assets; ✓ Financial Institution provides early information to the ARMA; ✓ introduction of electronic information exchange 	<p>Objective: $\uparrow eAM$</p> <p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ time from asset identification to seizure (days); ✓ proportion of assets for which measures were taken (%); ✓ ratio “detected \rightarrow seized \rightarrow confiscated/transferred to management” 	Increasing the effectiveness of arrest and confiscation
Regulatory and legal support	<p>Changing the legal basis of analytical materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ changing the legislation regarding the limits of analytical autonomy; ✓ establishing criteria for the admissibility of analytical materials in court; ✓ establishing a mechanism for verifying the reliability of data 	<p>Objective: $\uparrow eLE$, $\uparrow eJ$</p> <p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ number of cases of rejection of evidence on procedural grounds (per year); ✓ share of materials that undergo verification of authenticity according to a single protocol (%) 	Increasing legal certainty and trust
Military context	<p>Integration of the Financial Intelligence Unit into the control of military financial flows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ monitoring of military financial flows; ✓ formation of risk profiles for defense procurement; ✓ integration of FIU data with public finance information systems 	<p>Objective: $\downarrow wFIU$ ($\downarrow wLE$, wAM)</p> <p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ share of identified risky operations in the defense / post-war reconstruction sectors (%); ✓ share of prevented losses in these sectors 	Reducing the loss of public resources

Source: developed by authors.

The proposed directions for institutional and regulatory improvement of financial intelligence activities constitute an interconnected set of changes aimed at reducing functional gaps within the anti-corruption chain. This does not imply isolated strengthening of individual institutions, but rather the formation of a continuous architecture of interaction among the analytical, law enforcement, judicial, and asset management stages. Such an approach ensures procedural coherence, enhances the procedural admissibility of financial analytics, and minimizes information losses at transitional stages in the transformation of financial data into legally significant outcomes.

Under martial law, this institutional integration acquires a qualitatively new significance. The concentration of budgetary resources in the defense sector, large-scale flows of international financial assistance, accelerated procurement procedures, and the implementation of recovery programs create increased pressure on the public finance control system. The wartime context transforms the nature of financial risks, increases their latency, and complicates the detection of corrupt schemes. Under such conditions, the effectiveness of the anti-corruption mechanism is determined not merely by the formal existence of institutions, but by their capacity to function as a coordinated system.

Institutional coherence, digital modernization of analytical processes, early tagging of risky assets, and enhanced international coordination reduce the system's sensitivity to external risk pressure. Dependence of the final outcome on the weakness of any single link decreases, adaptability to changes in the structure of financial flows increases, and the cumulative loss effect—typical of sequential systems—is mitigated. In this sense, the proposed directions of improvement are aimed not only at increasing the effectiveness of individual institutions, but at strengthening the systemic resilience of the anti-corruption mechanism under wartime risk.

Within this architecture, financial intelligence plays a special role as the analytical center for managing uncertainty in the sphere of public finance. It is precisely at the stage of primary selection and structuring of financial transactions that the potential for subsequent criminal-law qualification, judicial verification, and effective asset management is established. Improving the quality of analytics, expanding access to data, and integrating financial intelligence with other elements of the anti-corruption infrastructure ensure the timely identification of threats, minimization of budgetary losses, and preservation of the financial base for national defense and state recovery.

Thus, the modernization of financial intelligence under wartime conditions extends beyond the traditional financial monitoring paradigm. It is gradually transforming from an instrument for combating money laundering into a structural element of the economic security system, integrated into the broader architecture for the protection of public finances. This evolutionary transformation does not alter the core functions of financial intelligence; however, it significantly expands its strategic role in ensuring state resilience in both wartime and post-war development contexts.

Conclusions. The study proposes a formalized approach to interpreting the anti-corruption mechanism as a sequential institutional system whose functioning is determined by the interdependence of the financial-analytical, law enforcement, judicial, and asset management stages. In contrast to descriptive approaches, the proposed model makes it possible to conceptualize anti-corruption efforts as a system of successive transformations in which the performance of each component directly affects the integral outcome.

The expediency of applying a multiplicative form of aggregating the effectiveness of institutional blocks is substantiated, reflecting their structural non-substitutability and the cumulative nature of losses in the event of reduced capacity of any link. This interpretation is consistent with the principles of the systems approach

and reliability theory and provides a quantitative explanation of the anti-corruption mechanism's sensitivity to systemic bottlenecks.

Particular attention is devoted to the impact of the wartime environment on the functioning of the anti-corruption system. The introduction of a wartime risk coefficient and an institutional sensitivity parameter enables the assessment of external risk pressure and its differentiated impact on individual stages of the anti-corruption chain. It is demonstrated that under conditions of war, the importance of institutional coherence and the system's ability to adapt to changes in the structure of financial flows significantly increases.

Based on the proposed model, directions for the institutional and legal enhancement of financial intelligence activities are systematized. These include improving the procedural admissibility of analytical materials, ensuring early detection of assets of corrupt origin, strengthening interaction with the judiciary and asset management authorities, and integrating financial intelligence into the oversight of wartime financial flows. The proposed measures are aimed at reinforcing the systemic resilience of the anti-corruption mechanism and reducing its sensitivity to wartime risk.

The obtained results provide grounds for considering financial intelligence not merely as a financial monitoring instrument, but as the analytical core of the anti-corruption infrastructure, upon whose effectiveness the preservation of public resources and the resilience of the state's financial system depend. In the context of wartime and post-war development, this entails a gradual transformation of the functional role of financial intelligence toward its deeper integration into the broader system of economic security.

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